

COVID^X

GAME CHANGERS

COVID-X OC#1

**Meet the 16 COVID-X Data and AI Solutions selected
in the Open Call #1.**

**These close-to-market innovations will support
healthcare providers to defeat coronavirus and to
save lives.**

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Table 1: Overview of COVID-X OC#1 Solutions

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Type</i>
SEGTNAN	Statistical Estimation for Group Testing Network Across Nations	Single
CAPTAIN-X	Coach Assistant via Projected and Conversational Interface to support the fight against COVID pandemic	Single
LOMT	Laboratory Optimizer for Mass Testing	Single
COVID-19 TRIAGE	AI-powered diagnostic decision support system screening patients for Covid-19 and assisting general practitioners to triage patients depending on their differential diagnoses	Team
C-ARM	Covid Armour: Large Scale Covid Risk Assessment Tool	Team
COV-ART	COVid19 software able to Analyse Risk Trajectory	Team
DDRRehab	Data Driven post COVID Rehabilitation	Team
KCOVRI	KAMU Digital Biomarker Based Covid-19 Recovery Screener	Team
Gaston scholar	Rapid and intelligent exclusion of COVID-19 using Gaston scholar (Self-Calibration of HOspital data for Learning Algorithms and clinical Rules)	Team
VADI	Voice Analysis for Diseases Identification	Team
Covid@home	Covid@home	Team
MADCAP	Management and Assessment of covid for Chronic diseAse Patients	Team
TRAJECT	Clinical Health Management of Covid-19 Hospitalized Patients based on a Trajectory Model	Team
Care4Covid	Personalized Care and Remote Support for Patients and Healthcare Workers at Covid-19 Risk	Team
AVIATE	vidAVo flights At The Edge	Team
C@H	COVID@HOME	Team

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3 Single Solutions

Acronym **SEGTNAN**

Title **Statistical Estimation for Group Testing Network Across Nations**

Abstract Group testing refers to sampling biological specimens from individual patients and pooling them into groups to reduce testing demand and resources in laboratories. However, there does not exist a standard methodology to determine the optimal number of individuals to be pooled together. SEGTNAN creates innovative AI software that enables individualized group testing at any laboratory.

Challenge #2 Innovative Diagnostics

Company SYNAPTIC ApS (Denmark)

Website *Under creation.*

Acronym **CAPTAIN-X**

Title **Coach Assistant via Projected and Conversational Interface to support the fight against COVID-19 pandemic**

Abstract Remote personalised care and monitoring assistant for COVID-19 patients using speech recognition and AI for patient monitoring as well as video projectors for personalized care. Monitoring as well as video projectors for personalized care.

Challenge #4 Remote Care

Partner CAPTAIN COACH P.C., Greece

Website www.captaincoach.gr

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Acronym **LOMT**

Title **Laboratory Optimizer for Mass Testing**

Abstract LOMT is software for COVID-19 mass testing - for diagnostics, screening, and epidemiological monitoring. It extends the standard processes of molecular testing for SARS-CoV-2 RNA with advanced data analytics and pool testing. The product can be used both in robotized and manual laboratories in a hospital, point-of-care, or mobile laboratory allowing the testing of 15 times more people with the existing resources by reducing the number of assays and the cost and time of each test.

Challenge #2 Innovative Diagnostics

Partner Jetware SRL, Italy

JETWARE

Website <https://lomt.jetware.org>

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13 Team Solutions

<i>Acronym</i>	COVID-19 TRIAGE
<i>Title</i>	AI-powered diagnostic decision support system screening patients for COVID-19 and assisting general practitioners to triage patients depending on their differential diagnoses
<i>Abstract</i>	0,1% of all patient consultations are Covid-19 related, while millions were either afraid or unable to access needed care. Lives have been lost as a result. The project develops a digital triaging tool for general practices, which (1) screens reliably COVID-19 infected persons to reduce the risk of spreading the virus, (2) helps both COVID-19 and Non-COVID-19 patients to orient themselves whether self- or professional management is required, and (3) assists physicians to diagnose more accurately.
<i>Challenge</i>	#1 Early detection
<i>Lead SME</i>	Symptoma GmbH Austria www.symptoma.com
<i>Healthcare partner</i>	Claudiana - Provincial High School of Health, Italy www.claudiana.bz.it

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Acronym

C-ARM

Title

Covid Armour: Large Scale Covid Risk Assessment Tool

Abstract

C-ARM enables EU clinics to assess COVID-19 contraction risk for patients in 32 languages. It takes regular voice samples without any app and creates a risk profile for new patients based on medical history, lifestyle and symptoms while showing a health trend for rehabilitating patients. Medical staff monitor and group patients to respond in bulk, multiplying productivity. API integrates to clinic's patient files.

Challenge

#1 Early detection

Lead SME

Softbrik
Estonia

<https://softbrik.com/>

Healthcare partner

AyurVaid
India

<https://ayurved.com/>

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Acronym **COV-ART**

Title **COVid19 software able to Analyse Risk Trajectory**

Abstract COV-ART focuses on data-driven monitoring, detection and prediction of early biological dysfunctions. It provides dynamic and personalized monitoring of laboratory test results to highlight early risk markers and suggest further tests. The University Hospital of Liege pilots the software within the COVID-19 to give a timely and accurate prediction of the course of the disease.

Challenge #3 Personalized Care

Lead SME Bio Logbook
France

<https://biologbook.fr/en>

Healthcare partner University Hospital of Liege
Belgium

<https://www.chuliege.be>

Acronym **DDRehab**

Title **Data Driven post COVID-19 Rehabilitation**

Abstract DDRehab aims at deploying a system for remote physical and cognitive rehabilitation of long-lasting coronavirus patients through the use of a smartphone. The solution merges different sets of clinical data to design and to adapt a personalised rehabilitation plan, which will be piloted with 50 patients.

Challenge #6 Recovery

Lead SME Ab.Acus srl
Italy

www.ab-acus.eu

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Healthcare partner

The Valduce Hospital
Villa Beretta
Italy
www.valduce.it/

CONGREGAZIONE DELLE SUORE
INFERMIERE DELL'ADDOLORATA
OSPEDALE VALDUCE

Acronym

KCOVRI

Title

KAMU Digital Biomarker Based Covid-19 Recovery Screener

Abstract

A recent study shows almost a third of recovered Covid-19 patients in the UK end up hospitalized again within 5 months of discharge, and one in eight die. KAMU Health, in collaboration with Finnish Lung Health Association, will adapt and productise KAMU's existing system into a tool that can be used for remote monitoring of patients after hospitalization. The service detects biomarkers for deterioration of the patient's condition to identify those who require professional intervention.

Challenge

Open challenge

Lead SME

KAMU Health Ltd
Finland

<https://kamuhealth.com/>

Healthcare partner

Finnish Lung Health Association (FILHA),
Helsinki University Hospital (HUS)
Finland

www.filha.fi/en

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Acronym

Gaston scholar

Title

Rapid and intelligent exclusion of COVID-19 using Gaston scholar (Self-Calibration of Hospital data for Learning Algorithms and clinical Rules)

Abstract

Identifying COVID-19 patients in hospitals is challenging as symptoms vary and the incidence rate varies greatly in time and location. The decision support system "GASTON scholar" safely excludes COVID-19 in more than 75% of admitted hospital patients, independent of a PCR-result. Therefore GASTON scholar saves test capacity and speeds up the diagnostic process to 1 hour.

Challenge

#2 Innovative Diagnostics

Lead SME

Medical Decision Support systems B.V.
Netherlands

www.gastonmedical.nl

Healthcare partner

Catharina Hospital
Netherlands

www.catharinaziekenhuis.nl

Acronym

VADI

Title

Voice Analysis for Diseases Identification

Abstract

VoiceMed identifies diseases by combining sound analysis and Artificial intelligence. The Machine Learning model detects vocal biomarkers of COVID-19 from the sound of cough, breath and speech. It provides instant results from VoiceMed WebApp or it can integrate seamlessly with an API to existing systems. It can be used every day, as it is quick to use without being invasive.

Challenge

#1 Early detection

Lead SME

VoiceMed SARL
Luxembourg

www.voicemed.io

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Healthcare partner

National Laboratory of Health (LNS)
Luxembourg

<https://lns.lu/en/>

Acronym

Covid@home

Title

Covid@home

Abstract

BeWell and its medical partner AZMM want to monitor COVID-19 patients in their home setting to investigate how they can be treated in the best way to lower (re)admission rate in hospitals. The obtained data and information about the home care monitoring will lead to a better understanding how to distribute the burden between the hospital care and the homecare. BeWell also wants to investigate how obtained data can be shared in a larger community with respect to all GDPR regulations.

Challenge

#4 Remote Care

Lead SME

BeWell Innovations NV
Belgium

<https://bewellinnovations.com/>

BeWell.
innovations

Healthcare partner

Maria Middelaes General Hospital
Belgium

www.mariamiddelaes.be/en/

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<i>Acronym</i>	MADCAP
<i>Title</i>	Management and Assessment of covid for Chronic disease Patients
<i>Abstract</i>	MADCAP targets cardiovascular disease patients diagnosed with COVID-19 aiming to support their remote care. The scalable solution gives remote support for COVID-19 risk management for prevention of infection, for managing remote treatments and for dealing with infection and post-infection cases. Gathering clinical and contextual patient data, it will support doctors to improve the care process.
<i>Challenge</i>	#4 Remote Care
<i>Lead SME</i>	AVATR srl Italy www.avatr-srl.it/
<i>Healthcare partner</i>	University Hospital Mater Domini of Catanzaro Italy www.materdominiaou.it

<i>Acronym</i>	TRAJECT
<i>Title</i>	Clinical Health Management of COVID-19 Hospitalized Patients based on a Trajectory Model
<i>Abstract</i>	Amalfi Analytics has developed Machine Learning algorithms to extract complex trajectories out of clinical records. This method is adapted to COVID-19 using data and knowledge from Hospital de Sant Pau, Barcelona, to understand the diversity of disease evolutions and predict resource needs. An app to assess risks for specific patients will be piloted at the hospital. By design, the project can be extended to most EU hospitals, to mitigate risks in most COVID-19 patients across the whole EU.
<i>Challenge Addressed</i>	#3 Personalized Care

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Lead SME

Amalfi Analytics, S.L.
Spain

<https://amalfianalytics.com/>

Healthcare partner

Health Management Foundation of the Hospital
de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau
Spain

www.santpau.es/

Acronym

Healthentia Care4COVID

Title

Personalized Care and Remote Support for Patients and Healthcare Workers at Covid-19 Risk

Abstract

Healthentia Care4COVID helps Hospitals and other Healthcare Organizations to improve their COVID-19 resilience and response by managing Covid-19 related symptoms of patients and health workers from remote and providing targeted support and care guidelines to them.

Challenge

#4 Remote Care

Lead SME

Innovation Sprint Sprl
Belgium

<https://innovationsprint.eu>

Healthcare partner

Hospital Agostino Gemelli
Italy

www.policlinicogemelli.it/

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Acronym **AVIATE**

Title **vidAVo flights At The Edge**

Abstract There is a lack of patients' continuous remote monitoring during hospitalization given the fact that this kind of equipment is expensive and has limited mobility.
The proposed solution performs low-cost real-time detection of health deterioration and enables highlighting the most critical Covid-19 cases exploiting edge computing.

Challenge Addressed Open challenge

Lead SME VIDAVO S.A
Greece

www.vidavo.eu

Healthcare partner Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Greece

www.auth.gr/en

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<i>Acronym</i>	C@H	
<i>Title</i>	COVID@HOME	
<i>Abstract</i>	<p>COVID@HOME is a remote care system for COVID-19 patients, with mild symptoms or asymptomatic, who remain at home and are monitored remotely by medical professionals. Collecting patient medical history and vital signs from patients, the solution can analyze biomarker results using novel published scoring algorithms and machine learning tools. It will assist physicians in their decision-making regarding treatment or hospitalization.</p>	
<i>Challenge Addressed</i>	#4 Remote Care	
<i>Lead SME</i>	Business and Bytes Ltd. (B&B) Greece http://dh.bandb.gr/index.php/en/	
<i>Healthcare partner</i>	Private Medical Clinic on Vascular Research (Vascular Research SA) Greece www.vascular-research.gr/	 VASCULAR RESEARCH

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